

Formation Constants of Acetohydroxamic Acid (*N*-Hydroxyacetamide) with H⁺, Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Indium(III) and Cerium(III) in Aqueous Ethanolic Media

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There is an important biochemical interest in the hydroxamic acids, as a result of the oxidised peptide (amide) group in a number of natural products¹. Ferric acetohydroxamate has been proposed as a source of iron in the oral treatment of anemia in animals and its formation constants are reported in aqueous solution². Mixed aqueous organic solvents provide a range of media where dielectric constant varies and proton-solvent interaction also changes. The study of analytical and biological applications of hydroxamic acids require the knowledge of ionisation constant and formation constant of their complexes with metal ions. The present communication deals with pH-metric determinations of formation constants of acetohydroxamic acid complexes with H⁺, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II},

Zn^{II}, In^{III} and Ce^{III} in 100 : 0, 75 : 25 and 50 : 50% (v/v) water-ethanol mixtures using Bjerrum-Calvin^{3,4} pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand formation curves (Fig. 1) showed that \bar{n}_A values lie between 0 and 1 in the pH range 8.0–10.2 (100% aqueous), 8.6–11.2 (75 : 25% water-ethanol) and 9.0–11.8 (50 : 50% water-ethanol) media for the ligand LH. The values of protonation constant $\log K_1^H$ corresponding to the ionisation of hydroxyl proton from NHOH group of the ligand in 100 : 0, 75 : 25 and 50 : 50% water-ethanol mixtures are given in Table 1. Brown *et al.*² reported a value of $\log K_1^H$

9.34 for acetohydroxamic acid at 25° in aqueous medium while Monzyk and Crumbliss⁶ reported $\log K_1^H$ 9.02 at 25° and 8.98 at 30.7° in aqueous medium at ionic strength of 2.0 (NaNO₃).

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ACETOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEXES WITH METAL IONS IN DIFFERENT WATER-ETHANOL MIXTURES*

Temp.=31°, Ionic strength=0.15M (NaCl)

Cation	Constant	Water-ethanol composition (% v/v)		
		100 : 0	75 : 25	50 : 50
H ⁺	$\log K_1^H$	9.20	9.62	10.10
Co ^{II}	$\log K_1$	5.70	5.60	5.97
Ni ^{II}	$\log K_1$	5.66	5.54	6.17
Cu ^{II}	$\log K_1$	8.13	8.07	9.12
	$\log K_2$	6.61	6.35	7.16
Zn ^{II}	$\log \beta_2$	14.74	14.42	16.28
	$\log K_1$	5.46	5.46	6.29
In ^{III}	$\log K_1$	7.42	7.59	8.25
	$\log K_2$	7.04	7.32	7.44
Ce ^{III}	$\log \beta_3$	14.46	14.91	15.69
	$\log K_1$	6.35	6.25	8.85
	$\log K_2$	5.28	5.84	6.37
	$\log K_3$	5.10	5.52	6.00
	$\log \beta_3$	16.73	17.61	21.22

*Standard deviations are within ± 0.04 .

The \bar{n} values lie between 0 and 1 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}; 0 and 2 for Cu^{II} and In^{III}; and 0 and 3 for Ce^{III} complexes with acetohydroxamate in different water-ethanol mixtures. The complexation initiates at pH 5.9, 6.5, 5.8 for Ni^{II}; 3.4, 3.6, 3.0 for Cu^{II}; 5.8, 6.4, 6.5 for Co^{II}; 6.3, 6.5, 6.2 for Zn^{II}; 5.0, 5.6, 3.0 for Ce^{III}; and 4.1, 4.3 and 4.4 for In^{III} in 100 : 0, 75 : 25 and 50 : 50% water-ethanol media respectively. The data (Table 1) show that $\log K_1$

Fig. 1. Proton-ligand formation curves of acetohydroxamic acid in different composition of water-ethanol media : (A) 100% water, (B) 75 : 25 water-ethanol and (C) 50 : 50 water-ethanol.

values are almost similar in aqueous and 75% aqueous media for each metal ion, however, the complexes are of greater stability in 50 : 50% water-ethanol mixture. The $\log K_1^H$ value increases with increase in ethanol concentrations (Table 1). With the increase in ethanol concentration, proton solvation of ethanol takes place. Thus increasing proton solvation by ethanol decreases the dissociation of the ligand (increase $\log K_1^H$ value).

Fig. 2. Titration curves for metal acetohydroxamic acid in 75 : 25 water-ethanol medium : (●) acid, (x) acid + acetohydroxamic acid, (□) acid + acetohydroxamic acid + Co^{II}, (Δ) acid + acetohydroxamic acid + Ni^{II} and (O) acid + acetohydroxamic acid + Cu^{II}.

Experimental

The purity of acetohydroxamic acid (*N*-hydroxyacetamide) (Sigma) was checked potentiometrically, and its solution was prepared in distilled water. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. The metal salt solutions of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were standardised⁷. Indium chloride and cerium sulphate were B.D.H. products. The mole ratio of metal-to-ligand was kept at 1 : 5 in order to fulfil maximum coordination number of the metal ion. Concentrations of

Fig. 3. Titration curves for metal aceto-hydroxamic acid in 75 : 25 water-ethanol medium : (x) acid+aceto-hydroxamic acid, (Δ) acid+aceto-hydroxamic acid + Zn^{II} , (O) acid+aceto-hydroxamic acid + Ce^{III} and (\bullet) acid+aceto-hydroxamic acid + In^{III} .

reactants used were $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ acid, $0.15 M$ NaCl, $0.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand and $0.4 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal salt. Total volume in each case was 20 ml.

An EC digital pH meter with combined glass electrode assembly was used for pH measurement in titrations against $0.1N$ NaOH. The titration curves for acid, acid+ligand and acid+ligand+metal ions are given only for 75 : 25% water-ethanol medium (Figs. 2 and 3). Similar curves were obtained for aqueous and 50 : 50% water-ethanol medium.

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